

TOWARDS NEW ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION SOFTWARE FOR STUDYING PERFORMANCE PATTERNS IN HARDANGER FIDDLE MUSIC

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ABSTRACT

Analyzing musical performances is a challenging and emergent field of computational music research, aiming to reveal performance patterns and link them to musical contexts. There exists a modest amount of computational research on Hardanger fiddle performances. The MIRAGE research project is currently contributing to this scientific body, developing advanced MIR frameworks that build on recent musicological research. This paper presents the development and evaluation of two Max/MSP/Jitter software applications^{1,2} for music analysis and data visualization that integrate contemporary research perspectives on the complex rhythmical structuring of *springar* performances, investigating how we can design user-friendly computational tools that explore performance patterns in Hardanger fiddle music, in collaboration with MIRAGE.

Based on a small questionnaire and a few operational tests, the study shows an interest in more effective software tools capable of revealing complex interrelations between musical dimensions in Hardanger fiddle performances. Additionally, the study highlights design considerations for tools aiming to increase the availability of computational music research in the field of musicology, such as cross-compatibility and integrated features that actively facilitate nuanced interpretation processes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Hardanger fiddle (HF) is a vital component of Scandinavian and Norwegian folk music heritage, dating back to the late seventeenth and early eighteenth-century [1]. With such a long-standing tradition, the unique performance patterns in HF music have interested folk music researchers and musicologists for some time. Today, researching performance patterns is an increasingly complex task that requires interdisciplinary research approaches, often bringing together musicology, computer science, psychology, library sciences, anthropology, and more [2–4].

There exists a modest amount of computational research on HF performances. As result, software frameworks and analytical tools that consider interdisciplinary and contemporary research perspectives on HF music are scarce. Current Music Performance Analysis (MPA) studies have also

suggested that more research is needed to evaluate computational tools for musical performance assessment, highlighting the demand for more precise conceptual and computational frameworks that increase our understanding of the mechanics behind musical performances [5]. The MIRAGE research project is currently contributing to this scientific body utilizing a transdisciplinary approach, developing advanced MIR frameworks that build on recent musicological research [4]. In collaboration with MIRAGE, this paper examines how we can design better and more user-friendly computational tools to reveal performance patterns in HF music.

To reduce the scope of the study, the presented work only considers specific rhythmic traits of *springar* performances, a particular sub-genre/style of Scandinavian folk music. The *springar* dance is considered one of the oldest traditional couples dances in Norway and remains one the most commonly practiced [1]. Most *springar* styles are rhythmically structured in triple meter (3/4), accompanied by solo HF performances. Interestingly, some regional variants of *springar* possess the stylistic feature of asymmetrical timing patterns, which refers to a systematic unevenness (asymmetry) in the duration and position of the musical beats. Recent studies have shown that beat-level variations in the asymmetrical timing patterns of *springar* performances seem to be related to "melodic-rhythmic" structures, in the sense that particular motivic segments are associated with particular timing profiles, suggesting that structural and other expressive features influence beat duration patterns [6]. Inspired by this novel research, this study presents the development and evaluation of two software prototypes that offer structural and multi-dimensional perspectives on the complex rhythmical structuring of HF *springar* performances, offering small contributions to computational music analysis, Scandinavian folk music studies, and to the overall preservation of important cultural heritage.

2. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Two standalone applications were developed for this study, implemented in Max/MSP/Jitter³, consisting of three modules, all designed based on HF performance data acquired from the MIRAGE research project.

¹ A video demonstration on the basic functionalities of the proposed toolkit: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fMtfBs5QBw>

² Source code: <https://github.com/AleksanderTidemann/hardanger-fiddle-performance-analysis>

³ <https://cycling74.com/>

2.1 Hardanger Fiddle Performance Data

One aim of MIRAGE is to provide detailed HF performance transcriptions with temporal and metric positions of notes through polyphonic pitch detection and rule-based models for automated beat tracking. As shown in Figure 1, the transcriptions can be represented as spreadsheets with each row being a note event and each column being a musical feature.

onset	offset	onpitch	offpitch	essential	bar	upmeter	lowmeter	offmeter
2.03928	2.43958	72.01000	72.01000	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000	3.00000	0.00000
2.05716	2.87347	64.97000	64.97000	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000	3.00000	NaN
2.87867	3.07252	72.01000	72.01000	1.00000	1.00000	4.00000	12.00000	0.00000
2.88399	3.08035	68.84000	68.84000	1.00000	1.00000	4.00000	12.00000	NaN
3.07252	3.30291	71.96000	71.96000	1.00000	1.00000	2.00000	3.00000	0.00000
3.08035	3.19274	68.82000	68.82000	1.00000	1.00000	2.00000	3.00000	NaN
3.25333	3.58168	64.91000	64.91000	1.00000	1.00000	4.00000	6.00000	NaN
3.30261	3.56475	71.99000	71.99000	1.00000	1.00000	4.00000	6.00000	1.00000
3.56475	4.11574	72.05000	72.05000	1.00000	1.00000	3.00000	3.00000	NaN
3.57092	4.09832	80.90000	80.90000	1.00000	1.00000	3.00000	3.00000	NaN
4.10975	4.24925	76.06000	76.06000	1.00000	2.00000	1.00000	3.00000	0.00000

Figure 1: Excerpt from a performance transcription of "Vrengja". While the onset and offset columns specify the temporal position of note events, the upmeter and lowmeter columns (inside the red square) represent their metric position. Performance transcription by Anders Elovsson and Olivier Lartillot.

Similarly, another MIRAGE objective has been to detect repeating melodic regions, or motivic structures, in the performances. Together, this temporal and structural information provides the data necessary to develop tools that explore the complex rhythmical structuring in HF performances with structural and multi-dimensional perspectives.

2.2 Application Nr.1

Figure 2: Application nr.1 consists of module 1 (left) and module 2 (right).

2.2.1 Module 1

By turning the MIRAGE performance data into something meaningful that users can engage and interact with, the first module aims to increase the data comprehension and general availability of HF performance data. This module features a graphical score representation that enables users to manipulate the beat-level rhythmical structuring of performances. The beat positions are indicated by vertical green markers, each with a unique label that identifies the bar and beat number. For instance, as shown in Figure 3, the green marker labeled "19.1" indicates the 1st beat of the 19th bar.

The predominant interactive component of the first module is the ability to make adjustments to the beat positions. Generally speaking, in HF music, it is assumed that some notes are more "responsible" for effecting beat durations

than others, meaning that adjusting beat durations should ideally affect notes to varying degrees. However, a less complex solution was chosen for this prototype implementation. When a beat position is adjusted as response to a marker displacement, all beat ratios are updated while note ratios within the beats remain unchanged. Consequently, when the score is refreshed, all notes are scaled to maintain their relative position and duration within the beats.

Figure 3: Manually adjusting green markers (purple when selected) rescales note positions and durations, effectively shortening and elongating the duration of the beats.

2.2.2 Module 2

The second module features an easy-to-use analytical platform for assessing the timing patterns of motivic segments in particular HF performances. The module consists of a custom-built JavaScript chart integrated with Max/MSP/Jitter.

Users interact with the plotting interface by entering measure ranges (from measure A to measure B). The module operates by comparing the user-requests to structural data previously loaded into the application. If patterns are found, i.e the range requested is subject to repetition, the module will collect the beat durations ratios from all the repeating instances and superimposes them in the plotting interface.

Figure 4: In this module 2 example, a user has requested to inspect a three-measure range in the performance. The module has identified that the user-requested range is repeated once. Therefore, the plot consists of two superimposed data entries.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the plot represents the size of patterns (number of beats) along the the horizontal (X) axis, with beat durations on the vertical (Y) axis. Additionally, color-coding is used to visually enhance the corre-

spondence between the plot data and note regions in module 1.

2.3 Application Nr.2

Figure 5: Application nr.2 consists of module 1 (left) and module 3 (right).

2.3.1 Module 3

The third module features a similar plotting interface, but designed to investigate if regions with similar rhythmical properties also share pitch content, general dynamics, and metric position.

Figure 6: Example use of module 3 displaying metric position of two note regions that share similar rhythmical properties. When investigating metric position in module 3, the vertical (Y) axis indicates beat indices (1, 2 or 3) within bars.

Users interact with the third module by manually highlighting note regions in the interactive score (module 1) before selecting a desired parameter. When plotting is engaged, the module collects note duration ratios from the user-selected note regions and scans the performance for identical regions. For example, if a user-selected region consists of three notes whose duration ratios are "40, 30, 20", the module will scan the performance for other note regions where a "40, 30, 20" duration ratio pattern occurs. If similar regions are found, the selected parameter, for instance pitch content, is extracted from those regions and graphed, as shown in Figure 6. In all instances, the plot represents the pattern size (number of notes) along the horizontal (X) axis with the various parameter values on the vertical (Y) axis.

3. EVALUATION

The system evaluation featured a combination of methods. First, two operational tests assessed the operational accuracy and general usability of modules 2 and 3. Second, a questionnaire was administered to collect systematic feedback on more aesthetic and conceptual aspects of the modules.

3.1 Test 1

The first operational test was designed to measure whether the data produced by module 2 was consistent with contemporary performance studies. The experiment was conducted on four different interpretations of "Godværsdagen", a *Halling-springar* performed and annotated by Olav L. Mjelva with transcriptions provided by Oliver Lartillot and Anders Elowsson. Six motifs were chosen for the experiment, all repeated between 2 and 10 times in the music, among which both two and four-measure motifs were considered.

First, all six motifs in each performance were identified in module 2 and used to calculate the standard deviation (SD) over the duration of each beat positions within the motifs separately, as illustrated in Figure 7. The output of this calculation left one metric per beat per motif. Finally, the averages of these values were taken, leaving one metric per motif per performance, indicating the amount of beat duration variation in the motifs.

Figure 7: By calculating the standard deviation over the duration of every beat index (the collections of dots in each red square), we can make a quantitative assessment of how much beat duration variation there is across repeating melodic sections.

As reference points, control structures were created that enabled comparisons between performances, as a whole, and their motivic components. The control structures were comprised of all beat duration ratios in a performance arranged according to their associated measure. By comparing the SD metrics of the motifs to their associated control structure, a precise evaluation could be made of whether variations in timing patterns were influenced by motivic structuring, or not.

3.2 Test 2

The second experiment investigated whether the current system implementation of module 3 was capable of identifying symbolic rhythmical patterns in the music. The symbolic rhythms in question refer to rhythmical figures in the

musical notation, consisting of collections of note-events. A symbolic rhythmical pattern occurs when a particular rhythmical figure is repeated in the notation, as exemplified in Figure 8. By locating the position of several such patterns, a test could be formulated, assessing if module 3 could identify repeating occurrences of symbolic rhythmical patterns in a performance that were referenced from notation.

Figure 8: Notation excerpt of "Vrengja". The red sections highlight a simple rhythmical pattern (eight-note triplet), among those repeated 4 times (or more) in the music.

The experiment was conducted on one performance of a *Halling-springar* called "Vrengja". Five basic rhythmical patterns were identified in the notation, consisting of either simple double eighth-note or eighth-note triplet figures. Subsequently, corresponding note regions in the interactive score (module 1) were located and used as input for module 3. Each sequence was processed multiple times. Finally, results were compared and cross-referenced.

3.3 Questionnaire Design

In essence, the questionnaire addressed the claim that there is a need for more interactive computational tools in traditional Scandinavian folk music research and queried whether the proposed toolkit possessed the capabilities to satisfy some of these demands, and if so, how it managed to do so. A short online presentation was given to all participants directly before the questionnaire that provided a comprehensive overview of the toolkit and information about where to download the tools so they could interact with the modules themselves. The questionnaire featured fourteen questions split into four sections, each with a central theme to enable a more categorical approach [7]⁴.

The first section categorized the participants' background and relation to Scandinavian folk music. The second section investigated whether there is a demand for tailored computational tools in traditional Scandinavian folk music research, examining the core premise of the study, while the third section assessed the conceptual approach, general functionality and user experience of the tools. The fourth and last section sought to gain knowledge about how the

⁴ Full questionnaire available at: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1nQ-YppEiD8NiHyoNptYSZy5lW8ZYQzh?usp=sharing>

tools could be improved by opening for un-restricted feedback and suggestions from participants.

The invitation to join the online presentation and questionnaire was primarily extended to all personnel affiliated with the MIRAGE research project, consisting predominantly of expert musicologists, HF performers, library scientists, cognitive researchers and computer scientists.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Operational Test Results

Results from the first operational test proved that the data produced by module 2 was consistent with contemporary HF performance studies, suggesting that beat duration variations in *springar* performances are influenced by motivic structuring. As shown in Table 1, a significant drop in timing pattern variation is identified when the data was re-arranged following the motifs. On average, motifs displayed 60% less deviation to their beat durations when compared to their associated control structure. It was also evident that there was no correspondence between the number of repetitions to a motivic segments and its beat duration variation.

"Godversdagen" Halling-springar	Performance 1	Performance 2	Performance 3	Performance 4
Motif 1				
Two-measure motif with 10 repetitions	1.276	1.178	1.963	3.396
Motif 2				
Two-measure motif with 6 repetitions	1.079	1.003	1.705	2.530
Motif 3				
Four-measure motif with 2 repetitions	0.856	1.062	2.015	2.429
Motif 4				
Four-measure motif with 6 repetitions	2.286	1.217	1.936	1.979
Motif 5				
Two-measure motif with 4 repetitions	0.760	1.390	1.345	2.111
Motif 6				
Two-measure motif with 4 repetitions	1.257	0.526	1.913	1.882
Mean	1.25	1.06	1.81	2.38
Control Structure				
Single measure with 98 repetitions	5.525	5.121	6.31	6.118

Table 1: Standard deviation of timing patterns of six motivic segments in four different interpretations of *Godversdagen*, together with control structures. Performances by Olav L. Mjelva.

Results from the second operational test showed that module 3 rarely managed to identify repeating rhythmical patterns referenced from the musical notation. Of the five patterns tested, only three were partly detected by the system.

4.2 Questionnaire Results

The online presentation and questionnaire session was held on March 4th, 2021, for 4 participants. 50% of the attendees identified as folk music researchers and performers, while the remaining participants represented other research fields like cognitive and computer science. None of the attendees documented to have interacted with the tools in the period before filling out the questionnaire.

The response showed a particular preference for the multi-dimensional analysis approach of module 3 and features that promote cross-compatibility, multiple import/export options, and consistent data standards. Furthermore, a clear majority of participants agreed that there is a demand for more tailored technologies in research related to Scandinavian folk music and that such technologies can contribute to our understanding of HF performance patterns. Other interesting findings indicated that increasing

the accessibility of the performance data through visualizations can be particularly effective in this regard.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Methodological Approach

With only four subjects completing the questionnaire, none of the survey results can be considered statistically significant. Similarly, the operational tests were prone to bias through design. Although both tests provided some basic assessments of the modules, shedding light on the general functionality and prospects of the prototypes, their margin of error is likely to be high due to the small sample sizes used. These methodological limitations directly affect how the results of the study should be interpreted and understood. In the author's opinion, the results should be interpreted more as valuable feedback, and guidance towards further development, than scientifically definitive.

5.2 Interactive Design & Structural Perspectives

A second limitation of the study was the lack of systematic and statistically significant data on the user experience of the applications. As result, we can only pinpoint that there is a potential for interactive tools to benefit research and our understanding of performance patterns. Precisely how the interactive design or visualization techniques proposed actually provide these benefits, remains unclear.

The specific design and functionality proposed with module 2 have real prospects of contributing towards a more comprehensive understanding of the underlying mechanics behind HF performances by giving users the ability to associate musical parameters with parent structural components [2, 3]. This was evident by both the questionnaire and operational test results. However, the question remains how we should interpret these test results within the context of the study. When linking performance parameters to various structural and symbolic layers, the number of variables in our analysis increases, rendering it more complex to make precise interpretations. Therefore, for module 2 to successfully increase our understanding of HF performance patterns, it should, ideally, include features that further help to guide the interpretation process. For instance, in an educational setting, we can imagine how much more useful module 2 would be if it offered integrated methods for calculating variability metrics or AI that automatically detected correlations across a multitude of musical dimensions.

5.3 Multi-dimensional Perspectives & Pattern Detection

The second operational test was able to provide some critical insight into the technical design, ultimately addressing whether the current pattern-finding implementation strategy would ever be capable of producing meaningful results without referring to symbolic or structural layers. In this sense, the second operational test was successful in its ability to accentuate weaknesses and strengths in the module's design, highlighting the potential benefits of such complex

capabilities to research and educational tools. With this in mind, it is in the author's opinion that an ideal implementation of module 3 should be built on existing frameworks and retrieval systems, preferably integrated into a software environment more advanced and cross-compatible than Max, such as a web application.

However, tools with multi-dimensional perspectives on musical performance patterns do not necessarily have to include complex pattern detection. In fact, most of the written responses and feedback advocated for alternative approaches, such as how bowing patterns are related to the melodic content or how foot-stomping is related to the beat positions. This response was not unexpected considering that both performance studies on traditional Scandinavian folk music and MPA are specifically interested in the link between musical practices and performance parameters.

6. CONCLUSION

A toolkit has been proposed, consisting of two software interfaces with three modules, offering structural and multi-dimensional perspectives on the complex rhythmical structuring of HF *springar* performances. The approach was motivated by the current capabilities of MIRAGE together with contemporary musicological research. The system evaluation featured a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches that assessed the operational accuracy of the software and collected systematic feedback on more aesthetic and conceptual aspects through a questionnaire.

Upon reflecting on the evaluation results in the context of the study's objective, a number of key findings were identified. First, there seems to be a demand for more tailored software tools in the field of musicology and Scandinavian folk music research. Second, when developing such tailored technologies, we should not underestimate the significance of interactive features and other aesthetic factors. Although the precise contribution of the interactive and visual design in the current interfaces remains unclear, it is evident that these factors increased the accessibility of the performance data, an effect considered beneficial to research on musical performance patterns. Third, for such tools to be relevant in contemporary research and educational contexts, they should be capable of examining the interrelations between musical dimensions, preferably how musical practices, such as bowing patterns or foot-stomping, impact various musical parameters and structural components, and vice versa. Fourth and final, in order to tailor to an audience with varying degrees of musical or technical expertise, tools with the proposed levels of complexity should, ideally, include features that further help guide the interpretation process.

7. FURTHER RESEARCH

Optimally, future development should see a software migration from Max/MSP/Jitter to a web application. A web application is easier to use, more maintainable, has better support for interactive and UI design elements, and facilitates more complex functionality. More importantly, a web

solution would render the application to be more compatible with other software and framework. A software migration would also invite the opportunity to upgrade and refine the toolkit features and general functionalities.

Finally, having more carefully designed features in a web-based solution could enable a better evaluation procedure with the ability to collect more varied data and reach more people in a shorter period of time. For instance, it would be interesting to conduct systematic user-testing of module 1 in various educational settings over long periods. Various types of user data could be collected through the web-based platform, providing a more in-depth evaluation of the module's prospects of becoming a reliable tool for musical performance assessment. Also, with an updated system architectures, it would be possible to explore whether the data formatting capabilities could assist in the creation of larger datasets for predictive models and other AI music-related technologies.

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